

Original paper

USING SONGS AS AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN EFL CLASSROOM

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: this article explores the benefits of using songs as authentic materials in teaching English as a foreign language (EFL), highlighting their motivational value and potential to create a positive learning environment.

AIM: the main goal of the study is to increase students' external motivation and enhance learning efficiency through the implementation of songs in the EFL classroom.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the study reviews various theoretical frameworks such as Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis and Eken's methodology on song-based instruction, alongside supporting academic literature on authentic materials.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: findings show that using songs fosters a stress-free learning atmosphere, improves vocabulary retention, develops listening and pronunciation skills, and encourages communication. The approach is particularly effective for young learners, including kindergarten students.

CONCLUSION: the study confirms that songs, as authentic materials, significantly enhance the effectiveness of EFL teaching, help engage learners emotionally and cognitively, and bring language acquisition closer to real-life use.

Keywords: EFL, ESL, authentic material, song, music, implement, method, atmosphere, rhyming.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ПЕСЕН В КАЧЕСТВЕ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ В КЛАССЕ EFL

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье рассматриваются преимущества использования песен как аутентичных материалов в обучении английскому языку, а также их роль в

образовательном процессе. Особое внимание уделяется созданию позитивной учебной атмосферы с помощью музыки.

ЦЕЛЬ: основная цель исследования — повысить внешнюю мотивацию студентов и облегчить восприятие учебного материала путем использования песен в процессе обучения английскому языку.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: в работе были проанализированы современные подходы к использованию песен на уроках английского, включая гипотезу аффективного фильтра Крашена и методические рекомендации Экена и других ученых.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: исследование показало, что использование песен способствует снижению тревожности, увеличивает словарный запас, улучшает навыки аудирования и произношения. Особенно эффективным методом оказался при обучении детей дошкольного возраста.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: полученные результаты подтверждают, что песни как аутентичные материалы могут значительно повысить эффективность изучения английского языка, способствовать формированию положительного отношения к обучению и стимулировать активное участие учащихся.

Ключевые слова: EFL, ESL, аутентичный материал, песня, музыка, реализация, метод, атмосфера, рифмовка.

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EFL SINFIDA QO'SHIQLARNI HAQIQIY MATERIALLAR SIFATIDA ISHLATISH

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatishda qo'shiqlardan autentik material sifatida foydalanishning afzalliklari va ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Qo'shiqlar orqali ta'lim jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va samarali qilish g'oyasi ilgari suriladi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — ingliz tili darslarida autentik material sifatida qo'shiqlardan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarning tashqi motivatsiyasini oshirish, eslab qolish ko'nikmalarini kuchaytirish va ta'limga ijobiy munosabat shakllantirishdan iborat.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda qo'shiqlardan foydalanish orqali chet tilini o'qitish bo'yicha ilg'or yondashuvlar, xususan, Krashenning affektiv filtr nazariyasi, Eken tomonidan ilgari surilgan uslublar va boshqa nazariy manbalar o'rganildi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, qo'shiqlardan foydalanish darslarda qulay muhit yaratish, avtomatlashtirish va so'z boyligini oshirish

orqali o'quvchilarning eshitish, talaffuz va muloqot ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Ayniqsa, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun bu yondashuv samarali natija bergan.

XULOSA: tadqiqot natijalari shuni tasdiqlaydiki, ingliz tili ta'limida qo'shiqlardan foydalanish autentik material sifatida ta'lim samaradorligini oshiradi, o'quvchilarni til muhitiga yaqinlashtiradi va mustahkam motivatsiya shakllantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: EFL (chet tili sifatida ingliz tili), ESL (ikkinchi til sifatida ingliz tili), haqiqiy material, qo'shiq, musiqa, amalga oshirish, usul, atmosfera, qofiya.

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As English language has already spread its popularity throughout the world, the number of people of different ages who show an interest to learn and speak in this language is also growing. Over a few years, different approaches of teaching English have been encouraged and implemented. Though these days' language teaching experts claim that mixture of different approaches and methods can be implemented depending on the goal of a student, the most spread and effective teaching method is considered to be CLT (Communicative Language Teaching). This method especially encourages the use of authentic materials, the materials that are not prepared specially for language classrooms but can be implement in the teaching process. Songs that are also considered as authentic material can also be of great use in the language learning classrooms. Very often music is the main source of English outside the classroom. Thus, using it in the lesson seems to be a good idea. There can be distinguished affective and cognitive rationale for playing a song during a lesson. As a matter of fact, affective reasons are connected with Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis. In short, it gives an explanation why some learners learn and others do not. The crucial thing is that students need to develop a positive attitude towards learning has it that, for effective learning the affective filter is must be weak. A weak affective filter means that a positive attitude to learning is present. Hence teachers' task is to provide a positive atmosphere favourable for learning. In this aspect music and songs may be one of the methods for obtaining weak affective filter. Eken enumerates eight reasons for the use of song in a language classroom. Firstly, a song may be used to present a topic, new vocabulary or a language point. Then, it may also be used as a practice of lexis. Beyond question, songs can be used as a material for extensive and intensive listening. Some teachers may use them to focus on frequent learner errors in a more indirect way. Not to mention that songs are a perfect source for stimulating discussions about feelings and attitudes. Learners may talk over with another in pairs or in small groups what happened in the song and then share their opinions with the rest of students. Additionally, songs may arrange a relaxed classroom atmosphere and contribute to fun and variety in language teaching. Finally, songs may be said to encourage the use of imagination and creativity during foreign

language lessons. Songs also give a chance to develop automaticity which is the main cognitive reason for using songs in the classroom. Automaticity is defined as a component of language fluency which involves both knowing what to say and producing language rapidly without pauses. To put it in other words, songs may help automatize the language improvement process. Essentially, the students should be placed in an environment in which it is possible to use the target language in a communicative way. As a matter of fact, the nature of songs is said to be quite repetitive, logical and persistent. Affective Reasons the Affective Filter Hypothesis is one of five proposed hypotheses developed by Steven Krashen. Basically, it is an explanation of how the affective factors relate to language learning. It is particularly appealing to teachers because it provides an explanation to why some learners learn and others do not.

Roger and Medley said authentic materials as exposure to real language in its own community. In these years the role of authentic materials in an EFL classroom has been discussed and debated by many language teachers. Nowadays their opinions have awesomely been insisting that English taught in the classroom should be authentic so that it can benefit the students' learning processes.

However, Nunam (1999, cited in Oura, 2000,67) has also defined authentic materials as spoken or written language data that has been produced in the course of genuine communication, and not specifically written for purposes of language teaching. Even though authentic materials are created not for learning purposes, they can also be used as learning materials in a language classroom. Martinez (2002) has proposed that teachers can implement authentic materials for the learners to listen for the general information presented and also he makes addition that by using authentic materials teachers can encourage students to learn something new for pleasure.

We are surrounded by music at every step, at home, at work, while shopping, on the bus or in a taxi. We listen to different types of music in different places. At these times, English songs also play in our ears. The use of these songs in an interactive way in lessons is important in strengthening students' skills. For instance: we can have pre, while, and post activities based on the songs to improve learners' listening skill. There are different ways of learning and teaching English thanks to lots of resources available. Some teachers prefer to rely on more authentic materials to enrich their lessons and expose learners to this language as it is spoken in the real world. Through using authentic materials teachers can engage even more students because the process of learning is imaginative and motivated. The best way of authentic material is it can be found everywhere from journals, TV programs, radio broadcasts, leaflets and so on. The single thing to consider is depending on learners' level to select the material.

Among those authentic materials using songs is also one of the best and effective ways to lesson in integrated way. Through listening to music students not only enrich their vocabulary but they feel relaxed atmosphere. Besides that, it's helpful it improves listening skills as pronunciation is very essential for learning a language.

It has been found that the ages from 2 to 6 is important period for brain

development. What's more, scientists have found that people can learn new language with native speaker proficiency until they reach critical period. Children under 10 have an ability to perceive new information without much difficulty that makes it also easier for them to learn a new language. However, traditional teaching can be overwhelming for kindergarten students. The burden of learning can be reduced by applying fun activities and games to the learning process. At this point, it should be mentioned that implementing songs in teaching English to younger learners is also greatly helpful. It reduces the feeling that one has to make an effort to learn something which is an important point for learners of younger age especially. After all, the best learning takes place when students have fun.

Songs can be implemented in teaching a new language in various ways and to boost variety of skills. Students of kindergarten age can learn new vocabulary in a fun way, improve their pronunciation with the help of songs. Songs that are made for kindergarten students usually has a lot of rhyming that makes it easier for them to remember. Such vocabularies as numbers, colors, body parts, animals, weather, etc. can be successfully practiced with young students. When children sing along the song, they have a greater success to develop better pronunciation.

Various ways to implement songs in teaching kindergarten students:

- to teach alphabet and one-letter (a, b, c) and two letter (th, ph, ou) sounds;

Teachers can search and find phonics songs of public domain in the Internet that are specially prepared for kindergarten students (e.g. a phonics song by A.J. Jenkins). While listening to a song a teacher can pause after a certain sound and ask students to repeat.

-to teach actions verbs;

A physical activity can be applied while listening that's students can be asked to try to repeat the action they listen in the song.

to teach vocabulary;

songs for children usually have a lot of rhyming and repetition that makes it easier for them to remember. It is easier for children to learn songs rather than separate words. Listening to a song and repeating and learning it can expand their vocabulary greatly. However, it is highly recommended to use follow-up activities to check students' vocabulary comprehension.

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